

The Impact of Language and Culture on Fostering Inclusivity in National Centers

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Annotation: This article explores the interconnectedness of language, culture, and the creation of inclusive environments in national centers. It examines how language barriers and cultural differences can hinder the full participation of all community members. The author offers practical recommendations for building more inclusive spaces where everyone feels valued and respected.

Keywords: inclusivity, national centers, language, culture, language barriers, cultural differences, intercultural communication, social inclusion.

In the context of globalisation and increasing migration flows, the problem of intercultural communication is becoming increasingly important. National cultural centres play a key role in facilitating cultural exchange and interaction between representatives of different ethnic groups. An important aspect of this activity is linguoculturology, which studies the relationship between language and culture, as well as their influence on intercultural communication [3]. Linguoculturology allows to reveal the peculiarities of perception and interpretation of cultural realities by different ethnic groups through the prism of language. As Ter-Minasova S. G. notes, language serves not only as a means of communication, but also as a tool for transmitting cultural norms, values and traditions [2]. National cultural centres that actively use language programmes and activities are able to significantly increase the level of intercultural competence of their participants and contribute to the development of mutual understanding and tolerance in society.

Intercultural communication is a process of exchange of information, knowledge and cultural values between representatives of different cultures. The most important component of this process is linguoculturology, which studies the influence of language on the perception and interpretation of cultural realities. Language mediates the transmission of cultural norms, values and traditions, which makes it a key element in intercultural interaction [1].

National cultural centres play an important role in the development of intercultural communication. They provide a platform for cultural exchange and interaction, promote mutual understanding and tolerance among representatives of different ethnic groups. Through language programmes, cultural events and educational initiatives, cultural centres help to overcome linguistic and cultural barriers [2].

National cultural centres actively introduce various practices and methods aimed at improving intercultural communication. For example, as part of language programmes, the centres offer local language courses for migrants and foreign students. Such programmes help new residents of the country to adapt to the cultural environment and integrate into society [3; 112]. In addition, cultural centres organise events such as festivals, exhibitions and concerts that promote cultural exchange and mutual understanding. These events provide an opportunity for people from different cultures to showcase their traditions, customs and arts, which enables participants to better understand and respect each other [3;

112].

One of the key aspects of intercultural communication is the development of intercultural competence. Intercultural competence includes cultural knowledge and understanding, the ability to communicate effectively with representatives of other cultures, and the ability to adapt to different cultural contexts. National cultural centres play an important role in the formation of this competence by offering educational programmes and trainings [1, 12]. Linguocultural learning is aimed at learning a language in its cultural context. It allows students not only to master language skills, but also to understand the cultural norms and values associated with this language. This approach promotes the development of intercultural communication skills and helps to avoid misunderstandings and conflicts arising from cultural differences [3].

Linguoculturology has a significant impact on the development of society as a whole. The study of language and culture contributes to the development of mutual understanding and respect among members of different ethnic groups, which in turn helps to reduce intercultural conflicts and create a more harmonious and tolerant society [1, 2]. As Johnson notes, 'linguocultural studies is a key tool for building bridges between cultures and peoples' [3].

National cultural centres that actively use linguocultural approaches make a significant contribution to the development of intercultural communication. They help to overcome language and cultural barriers, promote the integration of migrants and foreign students, and promote tolerance and respect for cultural diversity [3; 112].

The linguocultural aspect of intercultural communication carried out by national cultural centres plays an important role in the development of mutual understanding, tolerance and respect among representatives of different ethnic groups. The use of language programmes, cultural events and educational initiatives contributes to overcoming language and cultural barriers, as well as to the development of intercultural competence. National cultural centres active in the field of linguocultural studies contribute to a more harmonious and tolerant society. The results of this study emphasise the importance of continuing and expanding work in this direction to further improve intercultural communication and mutual understanding in the modern world.

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